

Scattering in the Gaussian Space in Semi-Classical Approximation

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Gaussian space is a three-dimensional Gaussian hypersurface embedded in a four-dimensional Euclidean space. The curvature of space depends on the distance to the origin. At a large distance, such a space is practically Euclidean, and because of this there are solutions to the Schrödinger equation that behave at infinity like plane waves. Without introducing any additional potential, the problem of particle's scattering in the Gaussian space is considered in semi-classical approximation. The role of the scattering center is played by the space itself, which is strongly curved at the origin. In this paper the complete WKB (Wentzel–Kramers–Brillouin) solutions to the Schrödinger equation have been built. Approximate expressions for the scattering phase shifts were obtained. The total cross section energy dependence was calculated numerically using these phase shifts. Both results display the tendency of the cross section to a constant value at high energy regime.

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1. Introduction

The idea of modeling interactions between particles via the non-Euclidean geometry has a significant spreading in the modern physics literature (see, for example, [1, 2]). In the present paper, we investigate the motion of a quantum mechanical particle in Gaussian space as scattering process. The space was introduced in [3] and realized on a three-dimensional hypersurface defined by the equation

$$x_4 = ae^{-\alpha(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)}, \quad (1)$$

embedded in a four-dimensional Euclidean space with the metric $ds^2 = dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 + dx_3^2 + dx_4^2$. Here a and α are parameters and have the dimensions of length and inverse square of length, respectively. In spherical coordinates r, θ, ϕ , the metric on the hypersurface under consideration has the form $ds^2 = f(r)dr^2 + r^2d\theta^2 + r^2\sin^2\theta d\phi^2$, where $f(r) = 1 + 4a^2\alpha^2r^2e^{-2\alpha r^2}$.

At high r values, the space becomes almost Euclidean one. In [3], the scalar curvature of a given space was analyzed and it was shown that the Schrödinger equation, which describes the free motion of a particle in a given space can be written in the form

$$\frac{1}{f(x)} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \left(\frac{2}{xf(x)} - \frac{1}{2f^2(x)} \frac{df}{dx} \right) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{x^2} \Delta_{\theta, \phi} \psi + K^2 \psi = 0, \quad (2)$$

where the notations are being used

$$f(x) = 1 + 4Bx^2e^{-2x^2}, \quad B = \alpha a^2, \quad x = \sqrt{\alpha}r, \\ K^2 = \frac{k^2}{\alpha}, \quad k^2 = \frac{2mE}{\hbar^2}.$$

At large distances from the origin $x \rightarrow \infty$ the Gaussian space is almost flat, $f(x) \rightarrow 1$, $f'(x) \rightarrow 0$ and equation (2) takes the form of the Schrödinger equation in Euclidean space

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{2}{x} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{x^2} \Delta_{\theta, \phi} \psi + K^2 \psi = 0, \quad (3)$$

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which has a solution in the form of a plane wave

$$\psi = e^{iKz} = e^{iKx \cos \theta}. \quad (4)$$

In this paper let us consider the problem of particle scattering in Gaussian space. We do not impose any additional potential, but believe that the curvature of space near the origin of coordinates itself plays the role of a scattering center. According to the general non-relativistic theory of elastic scattering [4], the solution to the original equation (2) at $x \rightarrow \infty$ should have the form of the sum of a plane wave and a scattered wave

$$\psi \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} e^{iKx \cos \theta} + \frac{f(\theta)\sqrt{\alpha}}{x} e^{iKx}. \quad (5)$$

We will assume that the scattering is isotropic in ϕ angle and expand the scattering amplitude and plane wave [4] in Legendre polynomials at $x \rightarrow \infty$

$$e^{iKx \cos \theta} \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (2l+1) P_l(\cos \theta) \frac{i^l}{Kx} \sin(Kx - \frac{\pi l}{2}), \quad (6)$$

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (2l+1) P_l(\cos \theta) f_l. \quad (7)$$

Hence,

$$\psi \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{i^l}{Kx} \sin(Kx - \frac{\pi l}{2}) + \frac{f_l \sqrt{\alpha}}{x} e^{iKx} \right] \times (2l+1) P_l(\cos \theta). \quad (8)$$

On the other hand, the general solution to the original equation is represented in the form

$$\psi = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} R_l(x) (2l+1) P_l(\cos \theta). \quad (9)$$

Assume that the function $R_l(x)$ for $x \rightarrow \infty$ can be written as

$$R_l(x) \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \frac{A}{x} \sin(Kx - \frac{\pi l}{2} + \delta_l), \quad (10)$$

where δ_l is the phase shift (compared to the phase of a plane wave in expansion (6)). Then

from (8),(9) and (10) we obtain the relationship between phase shifts δ_l and partial scattering amplitudes f_l

$$f_l = \frac{1}{2ik} (e^{2i\delta_l} - 1), \quad (11)$$

knowing which one can also find partial cross sections as

$$\sigma_l = 4\pi(2l+1)|f_l|^2 = \frac{4\pi}{k^2} (2l+1) \sin^2 \delta_l. \quad (12)$$

Thus, our problem is to find an asymptotic solution to the original equation (2) at $x \rightarrow \infty$ and represent its radial part in the form (10), thereby determining the phase shifts and, as a consequence, obtaining partial amplitudes and cross sections.

2. Approximate WKB solutions

Let us approach the problem of finding the phase shifts by WKB method. In semi-classical approximation we consider Planck constant \hbar as being small and orbital quantum numbers l is sufficiently large [4–6]. After separation of variables $\psi = R(x) Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ and using function replacement $R(x) = \beta(x) z(x)$, where

$$\beta(x) = \frac{1}{x} [f(x)]^{1/4} \quad (13)$$

equation (2) can be written in the form

$$z''(x) + h^2 Q(x, h) z(x) = 0, \quad (14)$$

where $h = 1/\hbar$ - is a big parameter in semi-classical approximation, and

$$Q(x, h) = f(x) \left(\frac{2mE}{\alpha} - \frac{V(x)}{h^2} \right), \quad (15)$$

where

$$V(x) = \frac{l(l+1)}{x^2} + \frac{2B}{f^3(x)} (e^{-2x^2} (-3 + 14x^2 - 8x^4) + e^{-4x^2} (8Bx^4(x^2 + 2) - 2Bx^2)).$$

To continue the analysis we set $B = 1$. Let us consider $V(x)$ as a sum of two functions $V(x) = f_1(x) + f_2(x)$,

$$f_1(x) = \frac{l(l+1)}{x^2},$$

$$f_2(x) = \frac{2}{f^3(x)}(e^{-2x^2}(-3 + 14x^2 - 8x^4) + e^{-4x^2}(8x^4(x^2 + 2) - 2x^2))$$

and plot graphs of the three functions $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$ and $V(x)$ at different values of l (see Fig. 1).

We see that the contribution of the function $f_2(x)$ to the sum is noticeable only at small values of the variable x and only at low values of l . For $l = 3$ the graph of the function $V(x)$ practically coincides with the graph of $f_1(x)$. Therefore, for sufficiently large values of l we can take

$$V(x) \approx \frac{l(l+1)}{x^2}. \tag{16}$$

The turning point is determined from the condition $Q(x, h) = 0$. Its coordinate is equal to

$$x_0 = \frac{\sqrt{l(l+1)}}{K}. \tag{17}$$

For convenience, we write the function $Q(x, h)$ in the form

$$Q(x) = Q(x, h) = \frac{K^2}{h^2} f(x) \left(1 - \frac{x_0^2}{x^2}\right). \tag{18}$$

According to the WKB method, approximate solutions of equation (14) far from the turning point have the form [5]

$$z_{x > x_0}(x) \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} Q(x)^{-1/4} (A \cos u_1(x) + B \sin u_1(x)), \tag{19}$$

$$z_{x < x_0}(x) \underset{x \rightarrow 0}{\approx} |Q(x)|^{-1/4} (C e^{-u_2(x)} + D e^{u_2(x)}), \tag{20}$$

where

$$u_1(x) = h \int_{x_0}^x \sqrt{Q(x)} dx,$$

$$u_2(x) = h \int_x^{x_0} \sqrt{|Q(x)|} dx.$$

The first approximate solution holds in the region $[x_0, \infty]$, where $Q(x, h) > 0$, at $x \gg x_0$, i.e. $x \rightarrow \infty$.

The second approximate solution is valid in the region $[0, x_0]$, where $Q(x, h) < 0$, at $x \ll x_0$, i.e. $x \rightarrow 0$.

Let us now consider the behavior of the function $u_1(x)$ at large x .

$$u_1(x) = \int_{x_0}^x S_1(x) dx = \int_{x_0}^x K \sqrt{(1 + 4x^2 e^{-2x^2}) \left(1 - \frac{x_0^2}{x^2}\right)} dx. \tag{21}$$

According to the well-known theorem of asymptotic methods [7], if $S_1(x) \sim S_2(x)$ at $x \rightarrow \infty$, then $\int_a^x S_1(x) dx \sim \int_a^x S_2(x) dx$ at $x \rightarrow \infty$. To estimate the integral for $u_1(x)$, we replace the integrand with the function

$$S_2(x) = K(1 + 2x^2 e^{-2x^2}) \left(1 - \frac{x_0^2}{2x^2}\right),$$

which satisfies the condition $S_1(x) \sim S_2(x)$ at $x \rightarrow \infty$ (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 displays the graphs of the integrand and the approximate function that replaces it (we took $K = 1$, $l = 3$ here).

Integration of the approximate function leads to the expression

$$u_1(x) \approx K \left(x - \frac{3x_0}{2} + \frac{x_0^2}{2x} - \frac{1}{2} x e^{-2x^2} + \frac{1}{2} x_0 e^{-2x_0^2} + \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{8} (2x_0^2 - 1) (\text{Erf}(\sqrt{2}x_0) - \text{Erf}(\sqrt{2}x)) \right), \tag{22}$$

where $\text{Erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt$ - error function. Let us take into account that for large values of x we can neglect the terms $\frac{x_0^2}{2x} - \frac{1}{2} x e^{-2x^2}$ and $\text{Erf}(\sqrt{2}x) \approx 1$. Then we get that $u_1(x)$ behaves at $x \rightarrow \infty$ approximately like

FIG. 1: (Color online) The functions $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$, and $V(x)$ at different values of l .

FIG. 2: (Color online) Integrands for $u_1(x)$ (left) and $u_2(x)$ (right).

$$u_1(x) \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} K \left(x - \frac{3x_0}{2} + \frac{1}{2}x_0 e^{-2x_0^2} + \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{8}(2x_0^2 - 1)(\text{Erf}(\sqrt{2}x_0) - 1) \right). \quad (23)$$

We see that $u_1(x) \rightarrow \infty$ at $x \rightarrow \infty$ and $u_1(x) \rightarrow 0$ at $x \rightarrow x_0$.

Let us now consider the behaviour of $u_2(x)$ at $x \rightarrow 0$.

$$u_2(x) = \int_x^{x_0} S_1(x) dx = \int_x^{x_0} K \sqrt{(1 + 4x^2 e^{-2x^2}) \left(\frac{x_0^2}{x^2} - 1 \right)} dx. \quad (24)$$

The same asymptotic method [7] is also valid for finite interval of integration: if $S_1(x) \sim S_2(x)$ at $x \rightarrow 0$, then $\int_x^a S_1(x) dx \sim \int_x^a S_2(x) dx$ at $x \rightarrow 0$. To estimate the behaviour of $u_2(x)$ at $x \rightarrow 0$ we replace the integrand by the function

$$S_2(x) = K \sqrt{\frac{x_0^2}{x^2} - 1}, \quad (25)$$

which satisfies the condition $S_1(x) \sim S_2(x)$ at $x \rightarrow 0$ (see figure 2). Integration leads to the expression

$$u_2(x) \approx \int_x^{x_0} S_2(x) dx = -K \sqrt{x_0^2 - x^2} - \frac{Kx_0}{2} \ln \left| \frac{\sqrt{x_0^2 - x^2} - x_0}{\sqrt{x_0^2 - x^2} + x_0} \right|. \quad (26)$$

From the resulting expression it follows that when $x \rightarrow 0$ the function $u_2(x)$ behaves approximately like

$$u_2(x) \underset{x \rightarrow 0}{\approx} -Kx_0 \left(1 + \ln \frac{x}{2x_0} \right). \quad (27)$$

We see that $u_2(x) \rightarrow \infty$ at $x \rightarrow 0$ and $u_2(x) \rightarrow 0$ at $x \rightarrow x_0$.

3. Complete WKB solutions

The approximate WKB solutions (19) and (20) are valid in the regions far from the turning point to the right and to the left respectively. To obtain the complete WKB solutions valid for all values of x , including the turning point, we use the method described in [5]. We need to build such functions of u_1 (in the region $x > x_0$) and of u_2 (in the region $x < x_0$) that will behave as (19) at $u_1 \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. $x \rightarrow \infty$) and as (20) at $u_2 \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. $x \rightarrow 0$) respectively, and at the

same time will be solutions to the approximate equation

$$z'' + \gamma(x - x_0)z = 0, \quad (28)$$

which is obtained from equation (14) by replacing the function $Q(x, h)$ with its approximate series expansion $Q(x, h) \approx Q'(x_0)(x - x_0)$ in the vicinity of the point x_0 . Here we denote $\gamma = h^2 Q'(x_0)$.

In the region $x > x_0$, such a function can be taken in the form [5]

$$z_{x > x_0}(u_1) = Q^{-1/4} \sqrt{\frac{\pi u_1}{2}} J_n(u_1). \quad (29)$$

This choice is due to the fact that for $u_1 \rightarrow \infty$ there is an asymptotic formula for Bessel function

$$J_n(u_1) \underset{u_1 \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi u_1}} \cos \left(u_1 - \frac{\pi n}{2} - \frac{\pi}{4} \right), \quad (30)$$

and, therefore, solution (29) for $u_1 \rightarrow \infty$ (that is $x \rightarrow \infty$) has the form of an oscillating solution as (19).

The order n of the Bessel $J_n(u_1)$ function is found from the equation (28) valid at $x \rightarrow x_0$. Moreover, due to the fact that $Q(x, h) \approx \gamma(x - x_0)$ for $x \rightarrow x_0$ we have

$$u_1 \approx \frac{2\sqrt{\gamma}}{3} (x - x_0)^{3/2}, \quad Q^{-1/4} \approx \frac{h^{1/2}}{\gamma^{1/4} (x - x_0)^{1/4}} \quad (31)$$

and the solution (29) at $x \rightarrow x_0$ takes the form

$$z_{x > x_0} \underset{x \rightarrow x_0}{\approx} \sqrt{\frac{\pi h}{3}} (x - x_0) J_n \left(\frac{2\sqrt{\gamma}}{3} (x - x_0)^{3/2} \right). \quad (32)$$

Substituting the resulting expression into (28), we find that the desired Bessel function must be a solution to the equation

$$J_n'' + \frac{1}{u_1} J_n' + \left(1 - \frac{1}{9u_1^2} \right) J_n = 0.$$

This equation is satisfied by the functions $J_{1/3}(u_1)$ and $J_{-1/3}(u_1)$. Therefore complete WKB solution in the region $x > x_0$ has the form

$$z_{x > x_0}(u_1) = Q^{-1/4} \sqrt{\frac{\pi u_1}{2}} (A J_{1/3}(u_1) + B J_{-1/3}(u_1)), \quad (33)$$

with A, B - constants.

We will use the same method in the region $x < x_0$. We look for the full WKB solution in the form

$$z_{x < x_0}(u_2) = |Q|^{-1/4} \sqrt{2\pi u_2} I_n(u_2), \quad (34)$$

where $I_n(u_2)$ is Bessel function of an imaginary argument. By virtue of the asymptotic formula

$$I_n(u_2) \underset{u_2 \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi u_2}} \left(e^{u_2} + e^{-u_2} \cos(\pi n + \pi/2) \right) \quad (35)$$

solution (34) for $u_2 \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. $x \rightarrow 0$) behaves like (20), that is, it has an exponential behaviour. As well as the solution (29), at $x \rightarrow x_0$ it must satisfy the equation (28). Now

$$u_2 \approx \frac{2\sqrt{\gamma}}{3} (x_0 - x)^{3/2}, \quad |Q|^{-1/4} \approx \frac{h^{1/2}}{\gamma^{1/4} (x_0 - x)^{1/4}}. \quad (36)$$

Therefore, when $x \rightarrow x_0$ the solution (34) behaves like

$$z_{x < x_0}(x) \underset{x \rightarrow 0}{\approx} 2\sqrt{\frac{\pi h}{3}} (x_0 - x) I_n \left(\frac{2\sqrt{\gamma}}{3} (x_0 - x)^{3/2} \right). \quad (37)$$

Substituting the last expression in (28), we find that the function $I_n(u_2)$ must be a solution to the equation

$$I_n'' + \frac{1}{u_2} I_n' - \left(1 + \frac{1}{9u_2^2} \right) I_n = 0.$$

This equation is satisfied by the functions $I_{1/3}(u_2)$ and $I_{-1/3}(u_2)$ and the complete WKB solution in the region $x < x_0$ has the form

$$z_{x < x_0} = |Q|^{-1/4} \sqrt{2\pi u_2} (C I_{1/3}(u_2) + D I_{-1/3}(u_2)), \quad (38)$$

where C, D are constants. Let us now find the connection between the constants A, B, C, D from the condition for matching solutions (33) and (38) at the turning point. We will include $\sqrt{2\pi}$ and $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ into the constants A, B, C, D and use the representations of the Bessel functions in

the form of the series [3]

$$\begin{aligned} J_n(u) &= \left(\frac{u}{2}\right)^2 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m (u/2)^{2m}}{m! \Gamma(m+n+1)}, \\ I_n(u) &= \left(\frac{u}{2}\right)^2 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(u/2)^{2m}}{m! \Gamma(m+n+1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Since at $x \rightarrow x_0$ the arguments u_1 and u_2 tend to zero, we can limit ourselves to the first terms of these series. Taking into account (31) and (36), and equating solutions (33) and (38) with we obtain that the integration constants are related as

$$C = -A, \quad D = B.$$

For the radial part of the wave function, we correspondingly obtain

$$\begin{aligned} R_{x > x_0}(x) &= \frac{\sqrt{u_1}}{x} \left(\frac{2mE}{\alpha} - \frac{l(l+1)}{h^2 x^2} \right)^{-1/4} \\ &\times (A J_{1/3}(u_1) + B J_{-1/3}(u_1)), \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{x < x_0}(x) &= \frac{\sqrt{u_2}}{x} \left(\frac{2mE}{\alpha} - \frac{l(l+1)}{h^2 x^2} \right)^{-1/4} \\ &\times (-A J_{1/3}(u_2) + B J_{-1/3}(u_2)), \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

where $u_1 = \int_{x_0}^x \sqrt{Q} dx$ and $u_2 = \int_x^{x_0} \sqrt{|Q|} dx$

From physical considerations, we require that $R_{x < x_0}(x)$ is not infinitely increasing at $x \rightarrow 0$. Let us analyze how this solution behaves in the case $x \rightarrow 0$. We take into account the expression (36) and the asymptotic formulas

$$\begin{aligned} I_{1/3}(u_2) &\underset{u_2 \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi u_2}} (e^{u_2} + e^{-u_2} \cos(5\pi/6)), \\ I_{-1/3}(u_2) &\underset{u_2 \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi u_2}} (e^{u_2} + e^{-u_2} \cos(\pi/6)), \end{aligned}$$

then for $R_{x < x_0}(x)$ at $x \rightarrow 0$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_{x < x_0}(x) &\underset{x \rightarrow 0}{\approx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \left[(B - A) e^{-Kx_0} \left(\frac{x}{2x_0} \right)^{-Kx_0} \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} (A + B) e^{Kx_0} \left(\frac{x}{2x_0} \right)^{Kx_0} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

The first term in the last expression behaves like $\sim x^{-Kx_0-1/2}$, that is, it increases without limit,

while the second term $\sim x^{Kx_0-1/2}$ tends to zero at $x \rightarrow 0$, since $Kx_0 = \sqrt{l(l+1)} > 1$. Therefore, it is necessary to take $A = B$.

The complete WKB solutions valid for all values of x are given by the formulas

$$R_{x>x_0} = \frac{A\sqrt{u_1}}{x} \left(\frac{2mE}{\alpha} - \frac{l(l+1)}{h^2x^2} \right)^{-1/4} \times (J_{1/3}(u_1) + J_{-1/3}(u_1)),$$

$$R_{x<x_0}(x) = \frac{A\sqrt{u_2}}{x} \left(\frac{2mE}{\alpha} - \frac{l(l+1)}{h^2x^2} \right)^{-1/4} \times (-J_{1/3}(u_2) + J_{-1/3}(u_2)).$$

Figure 3 shows the solution for selected values $K = 1$, $l = 3$, $A = 1$.

The solution $R_{x>x_0}(x)$ has the following asymptotic behaviour at $x \rightarrow \infty$

$$R_{x>x_0}(x) \underset{x \rightarrow \infty}{\approx} \frac{A}{x} \sin(u_1 + \pi/4). \quad (42)$$

Comparing the resulting expression with formula (10), we obtain the expression for the phase shift

$$\delta_l = \frac{\pi}{4}(2l+1) + \int_{x_0}^x K \sqrt{(1+4x^2e^{-2x^2}) \left(1 - \frac{x_0^2}{x^2}\right)} dx - Kx, \quad (43)$$

or, using the approximate formula for the integral in the last expression, we obtain

$$\delta_l \approx \frac{\pi}{4}(2l+1) + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{l(l+1)} (e^{-2l(l+1)/K^2} - 3) + \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{8} \left(\frac{2(l+1)}{K} - K \right) \left(\text{Erf} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2l(l+1)}}{K} \right) - 1 \right). \quad (44)$$

Figures 4 show the dependence of phase shifts on energy for various values of the parameter α . The reduced mass of the proton and meson is taken here for the mass m of the particle.

The phase shifts given by (44) we can estimate the total cross section of the scattering process. In the formula for the total cross section

$$\sigma = \frac{4\pi}{k^2} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (2l+1) \sin^2 \delta_l,$$

when summing, we will neglect the terms with $l = 0, 1, 2$, starting the summation from $l = 3$. We will also limit ourselves to those values of l that are less than $l_{max} = bk$, where for the impact parameter b we take the distance from the origin at which the space is practically flat. We believe that particles moving with such an impact parameter and higher do not experience scattering. We take $b = 8 \times 10^{-14} m = 0.4 \text{ MeV}^{-1}$. At this distance from the origin the scalar curvature is $R \approx -5 \times 10^{-25} m^{-2} \approx -2 \times 10^{-50} \text{ MeV}^2$.

In our calculations we take the following values of parameters $B = 1$, $m = 140 \text{ MeV}$, $\alpha = 10^{28} m^{-2} = 387.5 \text{ MeV}^2$. The resulting graph for the total cross section dependence on energy is presented on the figure 5.

As one can see, as the energy increases the graph displays the oscillatory behaviour near the constant value $\sigma \approx 400b$. For higher energy oscillations become lesser and the cross section is tending to the constant.

4. Numerical calculation of the total cross section

Let us rewrite the equation for $z(x)$ as

$$z''(x) + f(x)(K^2 - V(x))z(x) = 0, \quad (45)$$

where

$$V(x) = \frac{l(l+1)}{x^2} + \frac{2B}{f^3(x)} (e^{-2x^2} (-3 + 14x^2 - 8x^4) + e^{-4x^2} (8Bx^4(x^2 + 2) - 2Bx^2)).$$

We'll solve this equation numerically and use the units such that $\hbar = c = 1$ (unit-free), $[m] = [E] = \text{MeV}$, $[\alpha] = \text{MeV}^2$, $[\sigma] = \text{MeV}^{-2}$, $1 \text{ MeV}^{-2} = 387.5b$.

The case $l = 0$ should be considered separately. In this case at $x \rightarrow 0$ $V(x) \rightarrow -6B$ and approximate equation becomes

$$z''(x) + (K^2 + 6B)z(x) = 0.$$

FIG. 3: Complete WKB solution.

Since we must have $z(0) = 0$, we should take the asymptotic solution in the form

$$z(x) \underset{x \rightarrow 0}{\approx} \sin(\sqrt{K^2 + 6B}x).$$

Therefore, the initial conditions are determined by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 &= 0.00001; & z(x_0) &= \sin(\sqrt{K^2 + 6B}x_0), \\ z'(x_0) &= \sqrt{K^2 + 6B} \cos(\sqrt{K^2 + 6B}x_0). \end{aligned}$$

For $l \neq 0$ the initial conditions will be different. Indeed, in this case the approximate equation is

$$z''(x) - \frac{l(l+1)}{x^2}z(x) = 0.$$

Asymptotic solution regular at zero has the form

$$z(x) \underset{x \rightarrow 0}{\approx} x^{l+1},$$

and the initial conditions are $z(x_0) = x_0^{l+1}$, $z'(x_0) = (l+1)x_0^l$.

To find the phase shifts we must compare the numerically obtained solution

$$R(x) = \frac{1}{x}(f(x))^{1/4}z(x) \quad (46)$$

with the asymptotic solution $R(x) \sim \frac{1}{x} \sin(Kx - \pi l/2)$ at the end of the computational interval

(last period). They should differ only by a phase, that is our solution (46) must have the form $R(x) \sim \frac{1}{x} \sin(Kx - \pi l/2 + \delta_l)$. We determine the phase shifts as

$$\delta_l = K(x_{max1} - x_{max2}), \quad (47)$$

where x_{max1} and x_{max2} are the positions of maxima of the asymptotic and numerical solutions respectively in the last period. Now we sum for l from 0 to l_{max} , which is determined for each energy value as we did previously. We keep the same values of all parameters. The dependence of the total cross section on energy is shown in the figure 6.

We see that as the energy increases the total cross section tends to a constant value, approximately equal to $400b$. Thus, for high energies the numerically obtained cross section demonstrates the same feature as the cross section obtained though the approximate WKB phase shifts.

5. Conclusion

The problem of scattering of a particle in the Gaussian space has been solved in semi-classical approximation. Applying the WKB method we have found the complete solutions to the Schrödinger equation and the

FIG. 4: (Color online) Phase shifts vs energy for various values of the parameter $\alpha = 1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001 \text{ fm}^{-2}$.

FIG. 5: Total cross section dependence on energy calculated using WKB phase shifts.

approximate expressions for the phase shifts. Total cross section energy dependence was obtained numerically and using the WKB

approximate phase shifts. Both cross sections demonstrate the same behavior at high energy regime: tendency to a constant value.

FIG. 6: (Color online) Numerically calculated total scattering cross section.

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